

**Fatigue lifetime assessment of AM metallic components
according to a strain-based criterion**

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ABSTRACT

Over the last few years, the fatigue behaviour of Additive Manufacturing (AM) metallic components has been extensively investigated from an experimental point of view, whereas only few theoretical works are available in the literature. In such a context, the fatigue behaviour of AM metallic specimens under cyclic loading is theoretically investigated herein. More precisely, fatigue tests available in the literature are simulated by means of a strain-based fatigue criterion proposed by Carpinteri and co-workers. In order to assess the validity of the present criterion, theoretical results are compared with both experimental ones and those derived through the Fatemi-Socie fatigue criterion.

KEYWORDS: AM metallic specimens; fatigue life; uniaxial/biaxial loading; strain-based criterion.

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the last few years, Additive Manufacturing (AM) techniques based on an incremental layer-by-layer production have been increasingly used for the manufacturing of a wide variety of metallic components. Although AM techniques have already been known for more than twenty years, they were first limited to the production of prototypes [1]. Nowadays, thanks to the technology advancements, AM has become a reliable option for the serial production of structural components. As a matter of fact, many industries (including aerospace, automotive, construction, packaging and biomedical) turn to AM techniques in order to fabricate customized components with complex geometries, which are difficult (or impossible) to be produced by means of the traditional manufacturing techniques [2]. Moreover, AM process allows to reduce the weight of the components without joining and welding operations needed when using conventional techniques. In addition, there is a very little material waste in production of AM components and, therefore, a higher material efficiency.

In spite of the aforementioned advantages, there are still several challenges before AM techniques can be widely adopted by industries. In particular, uncertainty in the structural performance of AM metallic components together with a current lack of in-field experience with AM metals represent the main challenges to be solved [2-4]. The above aspects are more pronounced in the presence of complex cyclic loadings as those observed in real AM mechanical components during service

operations (e.g. aero engines turbine blades and medical prostheses) [5-7].

It is well known, indeed, that static mechanical properties (e.g. tensile and compressive strength) of AM metals are fully comparable with those of conventionally manufactured counterparts [1,8-10], whereas fatigue strength of AM materials is in general reduced compared to those of traditional metals [11-14]. As a matter of fact, internal defects (porosity and lack of fusion) [15,16], residual stresses [17,18] and high surface roughness [19,20], which are inherent features of AM metals, have a detrimental effect on the fatigue behaviour [21].

All the above features in turn depend on the employed AM technique (that is, powder bed fusion or direct energy deposition), the fabrication parameters during the manufacturing process (such as power setting, beam travel speed, scanning strategy), the feedstock characteristics, and the post-manufacturing treatments [22,23]. In addition, the microstructure of AM metals is anisotropic due to high thermal gradients occurring during the building process [24,25] and, consequently, the mechanical properties of such materials are more anisotropic with respect to those of wrought metals [26]. As a result of the above peculiar features, AM metals not only experience shorter fatigue lives in comparison to their traditional counterparts but also exhibit fatigue data characterised by significant uncertainty and large scatter [21].

Despite the great effort made by researchers engaged in optimization of AM process parameters affecting the mechanical behaviour [27-29], manufacturing a defect-free metallic component with an isotropic microstructure is not yet feasible. However, as is reported in several research studies available in the literature (for instance, see Refs [30-32]), machining and post-processing heat treatments allow to improve fatigue strength of AM metallic components. In particular, by machining the surfaces, the defects related to high surface roughness are removed and, consequently, fatigue cracks usually nucleate from internal defects. Note that, in many practical applications, machining is not possible due to the complex geometry of the designed components [33]. As has recently been pointed out by Jamshidi et al. [34], chemical etching has also been found to be an adequate surface post-processing treatment to improve fatigue performance.

Regarding post-processing heat treatments, the Hot Isostatic Pressing (HIP) treatment has proved to be very effective in enhancing the fatigue behaviour. HIP consists in subjecting an AM component to both high temperature and high pressure for a certain time, and is commonly used as a densification process in order to both shrink/close the internal defects and relax/reduce the tensile residual stresses [35]. After performing post-manufacturing heat treatments, the AM metal microstructure can be regarded as nearly homogeneous [4].

Fatigue behaviour of AM metallic components has been extensively investigated from an experimental point of view (for instance, see

the interesting review in Ref. [36]), whereas only few theoretical works are available in the technical literature. As an example, Zhan and Li [37] have recently proposed a novel analytical procedure for fatigue life evaluation related to AM aerospace components, by combining the continuum damage mechanics theory together with the machine learning models. Recently, Sanaei and Fatemi have developed a fracture mechanics-based approach considering the defect characteristics, in order to assess the multi-axial fatigue behaviour of AM metals [38].

In such a context, the focus of the present paper is on fatigue failure of AM metals, in order to estimate the fatigue life using a critical plane-based approach. More precisely, experimental multi-axial data available in the literature [39,40], previously investigated by using the Fatemi-Socie (FS) damage parameter to correlate such data, are here analysed by using a different damage parameter that characterises the strain-based multi-axial fatigue criterion proposed by the present authors in Ref. [41].

The current paper is structured as follows. The basic steps of the strain-based criterion here employed are summarised in **Section 2**, and the corresponding damage parameter is presented in **Appendix**. The examined experimental fatigue data related to AM specimens are discussed in **Section 3**, where a data correlation by using the FS damage parameter is also reported. Then, some remarks on the application of the above strain-based criterion to AM metals are made in **Section 4**, and the effectiveness of such a criterion in

fatigue life estimation is evaluated in **Section 5**. Finally, some conclusions are drawn in **Section 6**.

2. THE STRAIN-BASED FATIGUE CRITERION FOR TRADITIONAL METALS

The multiaxial fatigue criterion here outlined has been originally devised to perform the fatigue assessment of conventional metallic materials, which can be thought of as homogeneous and isotropic ones [41]. It belongs to the category of the strain-based fatigue criteria (e.g. see Refs [42,43]), is formulated by exploiting the critical plane concept, and can be applied to simulate both stress- and strain-controlled tests. Fatigue strength is evaluated by means of an equivalent strain amplitude, related to the critical plane, together with a unique material reference curve, that is, the tensile Manson-Coffin curve. The criterion has been applied to both plain specimens (also in presence of mean stresses) [41,44] and notched specimens [45,46], providing satisfactory results in terms of fatigue life estimations.

The flowchart of the strain-based criterion is shown in **Figure 1**, whereas the analytical formulation is detailed in **Appendix A**.

Figure 1

First of all, the material sensitivity to non-proportional loading should be examined. According to Papadopoulos' statement [47], if the ratio between the fatigue limit under fully reversed shear stress and that under fully reversed normal stress (that is,

$\tau_{af,-1}/\sigma_{af,-1}$) is greater than $1/\sqrt{3}$, the material can be regarded as non-sensitive to non-proportional loading. For the sake of simplicity, in what follows only the criterion formulation for non-sensitive materials to non-proportional loading is discussed. For materials characterised by $\tau_{af,-1}/\sigma_{af,-1} \leq 1/\sqrt{3}$, the Reader can refer to the novel formulation proposed by Vantadori [48].

The main steps of the criterion can be summarised as follows:

- (i) definition of the critical plane orientation, which is regarded to be dependent on the averaged directions ($\hat{1}$, $\hat{2}$ and $\hat{3}$) of the principal strain axes;
- (ii) evaluation of the normal, $\boldsymbol{\eta}_N$, and tangential, $\boldsymbol{\eta}_C$, components of the displacement vector $\boldsymbol{\eta}$ related to the critical plane at the verification point P (**Figure 2**);
- (iii) computation of an equivalent strain amplitude, $\varepsilon_{eq,a}$, expressed by a quadratic combination of the amplitudes of both $\boldsymbol{\eta}_N$ and $\boldsymbol{\eta}_C$;
- (iv) estimation of the fatigue life, N_f , by means of an iterative procedure.

Figure 2

3. EXPERIMENTAL CAMPAIGN EXAMINED

The fatigue data here examined are related to a wide experimental campaign recently performed by Molaei and co-workers on specimens made of two different AM metals, that is, the titanium alloy Ti-

6Al-4V [39] and the stainless steel 17-4 PH [40]. Note that, among all the experimental fatigue data reported in the original works [39,40], only those related to machining AM specimens subjected to HIP treatment are hereafter analysed and, then, simulated by means of the Carpinteri et al. criterion.

3.1 AM fabrication procedure, specimen geometries, and testing

A Laser-Beam (LB) based Powder Bed Fusion (PBF) system was used to fabricate the AM specimens according to the ASTM Standard B348. The fabrication process parameters included a laser power of 220 W and a scanning speed of 756 mm/s. Furthermore, for each layer, a thickness of 50 μm , a hatch pitch of 110 μm , and a hatch rotation of 67° were adopted [39, 40].

The materials employed in the manufacturing process were gas-atomized Ti-6Al-4V [39] and 17-4 PH [40] powders with the particle size range of 15-45 μm in accordance to the ASTM Standard B348. The chemical compositions of the powders consist of about 0.90Ti, 0.06Al, 0.04V, 0.003Fe and 0.002O for Ti-6Al-4V titanium alloy, and 0.17Cr, 0.04Ni, 0.04Cu, <0.01Mn, <0.01Si and 0.73Fe for 17-4 PH stainless steel, respectively.

Ti-6Al-4V specimens were built with an orientation of both 90° (named vertical specimens in the following) and 45° (named diagonal specimens in the following) with respect to the build platform, whereas the 17-4 PH specimens were only fabricated in the vertical direction (vertical specimens).

All fatigue tests were performed on thin-walled tubular specimens, with geometrical sizes reported in **Figure 3**. In order to reduce the surface roughness, both Ti-6Al-4V and 17-4 PH specimens were machined. Note that the specimens were manufactured with larger sizes with respect to those reported in **Figure 3**, and then machined to the sizes shown in the same Figure. After machining the specimens, their inside and outside surfaces were mirror-polished to remove the machining marks. The average surface roughness was about 0.100 μm for Ti-6Al-4V specimens [39] and 0.011 μm for 17-4 PH specimens [40]. These values of surface roughness were within the specifications of ASTM Standard E2207 (i.e. less than 0.200 μm).

Figure 3

Before testing, all the specimens were subjected to the HIP treatment. The HIP process consisted of keeping the specimens at 1120 °C and 105 MPa for 2.5 h under Argon atmosphere, and then solutionizing them at 1050 °C and 70 MPa for 20 min. Subsequently, the specimens were rapidly cooled at a rate of 200 °C/min. Such a treatment together with a scanning strategy consisting in a hatch rotation of 67° are able to almost completely remove the anisotropy and inhomogeneity of AM specimens so that materials could be theoretically treated as isotropic and homogeneous ones.

3.2 Experimental fatigue data

A closed-loop servo-hydraulic axial-torsion Instron machine (axial load up to 100 kN and torques up to 1 kNm), equipped with an Epsilon axial-torsion extensometer, was employed to perform both static and fatigue tests [49]. More precisely, static tensile and torsional tests (under displacement- and rotation-control, respectively) were carried out in order to determine the static mechanical properties of both examined materials (Table 1). Note that, for AM Ti-6Al-4V specimens, the static tests were conducted only on vertical specimens and, consequently, the static properties related to diagonal specimens were not measured during the experimental campaign [39]. Moreover, for AM 17-4 PH specimens, the value of the shear modulus G is referred to specimens with as-built surface, since such a property was not measured during the experimental campaign for machined specimens.

Table 1

Uniaxial (pure tensile and pure torsional loading) and biaxial (combined tensile and torsional loading with a phase shift β equal to 0° or 90°) fatigue tests were performed under both strain-controlled and load/torque-controlled modes [39,40]. Sinusoidal loading was applied with a frequency range from 0.25 to 5 Hz, as a function of the applied strain/load level. Note that strain-controlled fatigue tests were carried out in presence of plastic deformations, while the fatigue tests involving only elastic

deformations were conducted under load-control. All tests were performed under fully reversed loading condition (i.e., $R=-1$). Moreover, the strain-controlled biaxial fatigue tests were conducted with a ratio between shear strain γ and normal strain ϵ on the specimen surface equal to 3; the load-controlled biaxial fatigue tests were, indeed, characterised by a ratio between surface shear stress τ and surface normal stress σ equal to $\sqrt{3}/3$.

For AM Ti-6Al-4V specimens, failure was defined as [39]:

- (a) 10-12% change in load amplitudes (tensile or torque whichever occurred first) for fatigue tests under strain-control;
- (b) 1-5% change in displacement amplitudes (axial displacement or rotation whichever occurred first) for fatigue tests under load/torque-control.

Regarding failure of AM 17-4 PH specimens, no information is reported in the original experimental work [40].

The parameters of the tensile and torsional Manson-Coffin curves were derived from the uniaxial fatigue data for both the Ti-6Al-4V specimens (vertical and diagonal) and the 17-4 PH vertical specimens. Such parameters are shown in **Table 2** [39,40].

Table 2

3.3 Correlation of test results

The uniaxial and biaxial fatigue data of both Ti-6Al-4V and 17-4 PH specimens were correlated by means of the Fatemi-Socie critical plane-based criterion [39,40]. **Figure 4** shows the experimental

fatigue life N_{exp} plotted against the FS parameter, for both the examined AM metals. The solid red curves correspond to the experimental torsional Manson-Coffin equations related to vertical AM specimens. As was pointed out by Molaei et al., the FS fatigue parameter results in a quite satisfactory correlation with the experimental data, the theoretical data being inside the scatter band with factor 3 (see dashed red lines in **Figure 4**). For more details regarding the FS parameter, the Reader can refer to Refs **[50,51]**.

Figure 4

According to the considerations reported in Ref. **[39]**, only negligible differences in fatigue behaviour between vertical and diagonal Ti-6Al-4V specimens were observed after performing the HIP treatment (see **Figure 4**).

4. APPLICATION OF THE STRAIN-BASED CRITERION TO AM METALS: SOME REMARKS

In order to simulate the experimental fatigue test results in **Section 3** by means of the present strain-based criterion, some remarks are needed. As a matter of fact, such a criterion (originally formulated for conventional metals) can be applied to the above experimental data since the inhomogeneous and anisotropic microstructures of both AM metals were removed by

adopting, respectively, specific scanning strategies and post-manufacturing treatments [39,40]. More precisely:

(1) A scanning strategy with a 67° rotation angle (named hatch rotation angle) between successive layers was adopted during the manufacturing process [39] in order to obtain different orientations of the thermal gradient and, consequently, the anisotropy microstructure was considerably reduced [52];

(2) The HIP treatment, described in Sub-Section 3.1, was performed in order to shrink and close the internal defects, thus reducing the inhomogeneous microstructure.

According to the above remarks, the examined AM metals can be treated as homogeneous and isotropic materials.

It can be highlighted that the presence of both tensile residual stresses and high surface roughness (which are peculiar features of AM metals) are not taken into account in the formulation of the present criterion. This is due to the following reasons:

- As far as tensile residual stresses are concerned, the HIP heat treatment allowed to completely relax such stresses generated during the fabrication process (see Refs [39,40] for more details);

- As far as high surface roughness is concerned, it is well known that surface finish effect is more pronounced in HCF regime with respect to LCF one, since most of the HCF life is spent in initiating a crack [53]. On the other hand, a small crack usually starts relatively early under LCF regime, even if the surface is smooth; then, most of fatigue life is spent in growing small

cracks into the material at some depths, where the surface finish effect is almost negligible. Therefore, an effective method of including the presence of high surface roughness is to change only the elastic portion of each Manson-Coffin curve. In particular, the elastic slope of each curve should be reduced according to the procedure reported in Refs [53,54]. However, since the AM specimens here analysed were machined and polished in order to remove the high surface roughness, the elastic slopes of the Manson-Coffin curves have not to be modified.

Consequently, according to such remarks, the strain-based fatigue criterion (see **Section 2**) can be employed to theoretically analyse the fatigue behaviour of the examined AM specimens.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

First of all, for the materials being examined, the sensitivity to non-proportional loading is checked. In particular, the fatigue limits are derived from the elastic parameters of both tensile and torsional Mason-Coffin curves [54], proving that the ratio $\tau_{af,-1}/\sigma_{af,-1}$ is greater than $1/\sqrt{3}$ for both AM Ti-6Al-4V titanium alloy and AM 17-4 PH stainless steel. Consequently, the material sensitivity to non-proportional loading can be hereafter considered negligible.

As far as the mechanical properties are concerned, the following assumptions are adopted:

- For AM Ti-6Al-4V diagonal specimens, since the Young modulus E and the shear modulus G were not measured during the experimental campaign [39], the value of such properties is taken equal to that of the vertical specimens (see **Table 1**);

- For AM 17-4 PH specimens, the plastic parameters (ε'_f and c) of the tensile Manson-Coffin curve are not available in the original work [40] and, consequently, they are evaluated by using the practical rules proposed by Kim et al. [55], that is, $\varepsilon'_f = \gamma'_f / \sqrt{3}$ and $c = c_0$;

- For both AM metals, the effective Poisson ratio ν_{eff} is assumed to be equal to the elastic one (**Table 1**), since the Poisson's ratio for plastic strain is not reported in Refs [39,40].

Once the input data are set (see **Figure 1**), the strain-based fatigue criterion by Carpinteri et al. (**Section 2**) is applied to the experimental data reported in **Section 3**.

The comparison between experimental, N_{exp} , and theoretical, N_f , fatigue life is shown in **Figures 5** and **6** for AM Ti-6Al-4V and AM 17-4PH specimens, respectively. Note that the dashed lines correspond to the scatter band with factor 2 (i.e. $N_{exp}/N_f = 2$ and 0.50), whereas the dash-dot lines correspond to the scatter band with factor 3 (i.e. $N_{exp}/N_f = 3$ and 0.33).

Figure 5

Figure 6

The above graphs prove that the strain-based fatigue criterion provides results mainly falling within the scatter band with factor 3, independent of both the specimen build direction and the applied loading. More precisely, for AM Ti-6Al-4V specimens, 57% of the results fall within the scatter band with factor 2, whereas 86% of the results fall within the scatter band with factor 3. Regarding AM 17-4 PH specimens, 44% of theoretical fatigue life values are included into scatter band with factor 2, whereas 78% of such values are included into scatter band with factor 3. In any case, when results do not fall within the reference bands, the predictions made by the present criterion are on the conservative side.

Figure 7 shows the experimental fatigue life N_{exp} against the equivalent strain amplitude $\varepsilon_{eq,a}$, for both examined AM metals. The solid blue lines are related to the experimental tensile Manson-Coffin curves. Such graphs indicate that $\varepsilon_{eq,a}$ results in a quite satisfactory correlation with the experimental fatigue data, since almost all theoretical results lie close to the experimental curves.

Figure 7

By comparing the results in **Figure 7** with those reported in **Figure 4**, it can be remarked that the accuracy of the present criterion in estimating fatigue strength of AM metals is very

similar to that of the Fatemi-Socie (FS) criterion. As a matter of fact:

- For AM Ti-6Al-4V specimens (considering both build directions), the percentage of results included into scatter band with factor 3 is equal to 86% and 83% by applying the present criterion (**Figures 7(a)** and **7(b)**) and the FS criterion (**Figure 4(a)**), respectively;

- For AM 17-4 PH specimens, 78% and 89% of the theoretical results related to the present criterion (**Figure 7(c)**) and the FS criterion (**Figure 4(b)**), respectively, fall into scatter band with factor 3.

Finally, the quality of the present results can be statistically interpreted by means of the root mean square (RMS) error method [56]. In particular, the mean square error T_{RMS} is computed as follows:

$$T_{RMS} = 10^{E_{RMS}} \quad \text{with} \quad E_{RMS} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^j \log^2(N_{exp}/N_f)_i}{j}} \quad (1)$$

where j is the number of the examined fatigue data.

Tables 3 and **4** show the T_{RMS} values related to AM Ti-6Al-4V and AM 17-4PH specimens, respectively, in accordance with both the present strain-based fatigue criterion and the FS criterion. In particular, the T_{RMS} values are computed by considering the different loadings here examined, that is, tensile, torsional and biaxial fatigue loading. Regarding AM Ti-6Al-4V specimens, the

results do not take into account the build direction (**Table 3**), since no evident differences are observed in terms of fatigue behaviour between vertical and diagonal specimens.

The analysis of the results in terms of the mean square error clearly indicates that:

- For all fatigue tests, similar accuracy is noticed by using the present criterion and the FS criterion, and this holds true for both the examined AM metals;

- For tensile fatigue tests, higher accuracy is gained by applying the present criterion, with a decrease of the T_{RMS} values up to 54% with respect to those deduced through the FS criterion for AM Ti-6Al-4V specimens;

- For torsional fatigue tests, the most accurate results are determined by employing the FS criterion, since the values of T_{RMS} are lower than 2 for both the examined AM metals;

- For biaxial fatigue tests, slightly better accuracy is reached by means of the FS criterion, characterized by lower T_{RMS} values than those determined through the present criterion.

Table 3

Table 4

6. CONCLUSIONS

In the present paper, the fatigue behaviour of AM metallic specimens under both uniaxial and biaxial cyclic loading has been theoretically examined. In particular, several fatigue tests

available in the literature have been simulated by means of the strain-based multiaxial fatigue criterion proposed by Carpinteri and co-workers.

The agreement between experimental data and estimated fatigue lives is satisfactory for both AM metals examined. In particular, considering the different loading conditions:

- > For tensile fatigue loading, all estimated fatigue lives related to both AM Ti-6Al-4V and AM 17-4 PH specimens are included into scatter band with factor 3;
- > For torsional fatigue loading, 71% and 67% of the results related to AM Ti-6Al-4V and AM 17-4 PH specimens, respectively, fall within the scatter band with factor 3;
- > For biaxial fatigue loading, 80% and 75% of estimated fatigue lives related to AM Ti-6Al-4V and AM 17-4 PH specimens, respectively, are included into scatter band with factor 3.

Based on such encouraging results, the validity of the present criterion is also confirmed for AM materials. Moreover, the obtained accuracy level is very similar to that determined by using the FS damage parameter.

All the remarks reported above seem to strongly support the conclusion that the present criterion can be considered as a promising engineering tool for fatigue design of AM metallic components. However, more work needs to be done in order to safely extend the use of such a criterion to other AM metals subjected to more complex loading conditions. Moreover, the presence of high surface roughness will be also taken into account

in the criterion formulation by reducing the elastic parameters of the Manson-Coffin curves.

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NOMENCLATURE

$1, 2, 3$	principal strain directions
$\hat{1}, \hat{2}, \hat{3}$	averaged principal strain directions
b	fatigue strength exponent under normal strain
b_0	fatigue strength exponent under shear strain
c	fatigue ductility exponent under normal strain
c_0	fatigue ductility exponent under shear strain
E	Young modulus
G	shear modulus
N_{exp}	experimental fatigue life
N_f	fatigue life
P	verification point
P_{uvw}	local reference system attached to the critical plane
P_{rtz}	fixed reference system
T	period
T_{RMS}	mean square error
t	time
\mathbf{w}	unit vector normal to the critical plane
W	weight function
β	phase shift between tensile and torsional loading
γ	applied shear strain
γ'_f	fatigue ductility coefficient under shear strain
δ	off-angle defining the normal to the critical plane
$\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_3$	principal strains
ε	applied normal strain
$\varepsilon_{eq,a}$	equivalent normal strain amplitude
ε'_f	fatigue ductility coefficient under normal strain
$\boldsymbol{\eta}$	displacement vector at verification point P , related to the critical plane
$\boldsymbol{\eta}_N$	normal vector component of $\boldsymbol{\eta}$, related to the critical plane

η_c	tangential vector component of η , related to the critical plane
ν_e	elastic Poisson ratio
ν_{eff}	effective Poisson ratio
σ	surface normal stress
σ'_f	fatigue strength coefficient under normal strain
$\sigma_{af,-1}$	fully-reversed normal stress fatigue strength
τ	surface shear stress
τ'_f	fatigue strength coefficient under shear strain
$\tau_{af,-1}$	fully-reversed shear stress fatigue strength
ϕ, θ, ψ	principal Euler angles

Acronyms

AM	Additive Manufacturing
FS	Fatemi-Socie
HIP	Hot Isotatic Pressing
LB	Laser-Beam
PBF	Powder Bed Fusion

Appendix A – Strain-based fatigue criterion formulation

The theoretical concepts of the strain-based fatigue criterion proposed by Carpinteri and co-workers [41] are here outlined.

Let us consider the strain state at a material point P (located on the component surface), with respect to the fixed reference system $Prtz$ (see **Figure 2**). The principal strains ε_1 , ε_2 and ε_3 (with $\varepsilon_1 \geq \varepsilon_2 \geq \varepsilon_3$) and the corresponding principal directions 1, 2 and 3 (identified by means of the principal Euler angles ϕ , θ and ψ) have to be determined. Since the principal strain directions are usually time-varying under multiaxial cyclic loading, Carpinteri et al. suggested to evaluate the averaged principal strain directions $\hat{1}$, $\hat{2}$ and $\hat{3}$ by averaging the principal Euler angles on the period T :

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\phi} &= \frac{1}{W} \int_0^T \phi(t) W(t) dt \\ \hat{\theta} &= \frac{1}{W} \int_0^T \theta(t) W(t) dt \\ \hat{\psi} &= \frac{1}{W} \int_0^T \psi(t) W(t) dt\end{aligned}\tag{A.1}$$

where $W(T)$ is the weight function expressed by

$$W(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & \varepsilon_1(t) < \varepsilon_{1,max} \\ 1, & \varepsilon_1(t) = \varepsilon_{1,max} \end{cases}\tag{A.2}$$

being $\varepsilon_{1,max}$ the maximum value achieved by $\varepsilon_1(t)$ during T .

Then, the orientation of the critical plane (that is, the verification plane for fatigue life evaluation) is defined through an off-angle δ (in the plane $\hat{1}\hat{3}$) formed by the normal \mathbf{w} to the critical plane and the $\hat{1}$ -axis. The following empirical expression is employed to compute the above off-angle δ :

$$\delta = \frac{3}{2} \left[1 - \left(\frac{1}{2(1+\nu_{eff})} \frac{\gamma_a}{\varepsilon_a} \right)^2 \right] 45^\circ \quad (\text{A.3})$$

ν_{eff} being the effective Poisson ratio. Moreover, ε_a and γ_a are defined by means of the tensile and torsional Manson-Coffin equations, respectively:

$$\varepsilon_a = \frac{\sigma'_f}{E} (2N_f)^{b_0} + \varepsilon'_f (2N_f)^c \quad (\text{A.4a})$$

$$\gamma_a = \frac{\tau'_f}{G} (2N_f)^{b_0} + \gamma'_f (2N_f)^{c_0} \quad (\text{A.4b})$$

where N_f is the number of loading cycles to failure, E and G are the Young modulus and shear modulus, respectively, and σ'_f , ε'_f , b_0 , c , τ'_f , γ'_f , b_0 , c_0 are material constants, which can be deduced by running appropriate experimental tests. Note that the above δ expression is able to take into account the nature of fracture as is reported in Refs **[41,43,44]**.

Now let us consider the local reference system, $Puvw$, attached to the critical plane: the u -axis is the intersection line between the critical plane and the plane defined by the normal vector \mathbf{w} and the z -axis, and the v -axis is such as to form a right-handed system together with the u -axis and the w -axis.

The displacement vector $\boldsymbol{\eta}$ at point P , computed from the strain tensor expressed with respect to $Puvw$, may be decomposed in a normal vector $\boldsymbol{\eta}_N$ and a tangential vector $\boldsymbol{\eta}_C$. In particular, since the direction of $\boldsymbol{\eta}_N$ is time-invariant, the corresponding amplitude in a loading cycle, $\eta_{N,a}$, can easily be computed. On the other hand, the direction of $\boldsymbol{\eta}_C$ changes during a loading cycle, and the definition of the corresponding amplitude, $\eta_{C,a}$, is not unique. Several methods to evaluate such an amplitude are available in the literature, and the Prismatic Hull method is here implemented in the criterion formulation.

Then, the fatigue lifetime is assessed by means of an equivalent strain amplitude $\varepsilon_{eq,a}$ (also named damage parameter), together with a unique material reference curve (i.e. the tensile Manson-Coffin curve, Eq. (A.4a)). More precisely, $\varepsilon_{eq,a}$ is expressed by quadratically combining the amplitudes of both the normal, $\eta_{N,a}$, and the tangential, $\eta_{C,a}$, displacement vectors acting on the critical plane:

$$\varepsilon_{eq,a} = \sqrt{(\eta_{N,a})^2 + \left(\frac{\varepsilon_a}{\gamma_a}\right)^2 (\eta_{C,a})^2} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

being ε_a and γ_a given by Eqs (A.4). By equating Eq. (A.5) with Eq. (A.4a), the number N_f of loading cycles to failure can be computed through an iterative procedure.

Figure 1. Flowchart of the strain-based fatigue criterion [41]. The damage parameter is in the blue lozenge.

Figure 2. Global reference frame $Prtz$ and local reference frame $Puvw$, together with the components of displacement vector $\boldsymbol{\eta}$ related to the critical plane Δ .

Figure 3. Specimen geometry and sizes (expressed in mm). The value of d is equal to 12.7 mm and 14 mm for Ti-6Al-4V specimens and 17-4 PH specimens, respectively [39,40].

Table 1. Static mechanical properties of Ti-6Al-4V specimens [39] and 17-4 PH specimens [40].

SPECIMEN TYPE	E	G	ν_e	σ_u	σ_y
Ti-6Al-4V - VERTICAL	118.9 GPa	45.7 GPa	0.3	1003 MPa	886 MPa
17-4 PH - VERTICAL	203.1 GPa	78.8 GPa	0.3	1193 MPa	1154 MPa

Table 2. Fatigue properties of Ti-6Al-4V specimens (vertical and diagonal) [39] and 17-4 PH vertical specimens [40].

	Ti-6Al-4V VERTICAL	Ti-6Al-4V DIAGONAL	17-4 PH VERTICAL
σ'_f [MPa]	1240	1573	1976
b [-]	-0.0547	-0.0776	-0.0740
ε'_f [-]	1.04	2.61	-
c [-]	-0.735	-0.879	-
τ'_f [MPa]	683	588	1026
b_0 [-]	-0.0417	-0.0282	-0.0550
γ'_f [-]	0.40	0.41	4.69
c_0 [-]	-0.481	-0.453	-0.916

Figure 4. Uniaxial and biaxial fatigue data correlation by means of the Fatemi-Socie (FS) damage parameter for: (a) AM Ti-6Al-4V specimens [39] and (b) AM 17-4 PH specimens [40].

In the legend, V stands for vertical specimens and D for diagonal specimens.

Figure 5. Comparison between theoretical, N_f , and experimental, N_{exp} , fatigue life for AM Ti-6Al-4V specimens [39]: (a) tensile loading; (b) torsional loading; (c) biaxial loading.

Figure 6. Comparison between theoretical, N_f , and experimental, N_{exp} , fatigue life for AM 17-4 PH specimens [40]: (a) tensile loading; (b) torsional loading; (c) biaxial loading.

Figure 7. Fatigue life experimental data plotted in terms of the equivalent strain amplitude $\epsilon_{eq,a}$ (damage parameter) for: (a) AM Ti-6Al-4V vertical specimens; (b) AM Ti-6Al-4V diagonal specimens; (c) AM 17-4 PH specimens.

Table 3. Mean square error T_{RMS} computed for AM Ti-6Al-4V specimens.

Ti-6Al-4V	T_{RMS}	T_{RMS}
	Present study	FS- damage par.
TENSION	1.54	3.37
TORSION	3.30	1.96
BIAXIAL	2.76	1.88

Table 4. Mean square error T_{RMS} computed for AM 17-4 PH specimens.

AM 17-4 PH	T_{RMS}	T_{RMS}
	Present study	FS- damage par.
TENSION	1.32	2.08
TORSION	2.91	1.48
BIAXIAL	2.52	1.89